

SKILLS IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES (ICT) AND DIGITAL COMPETENCIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10617064>

Annotation. This abstract explores the significance of skills in Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and Digital Competencies. It examines the societal impact on legislation and development of concepts for transitioning to a digital society. The discussion emphasizes the introduction of "digital literacy" and "digital competence" comparing them with ICT competence.

Keywords: information and communication technologies (ICT), digital competencies, digital literacy, digital economy, educational technology, UNESCO ICT competencies.

Skills in the field of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and digital competencies are crucial in today's society. Changes that have occurred in society are reflected in Uzbekistan and international legislation. Legal, socio-economic, cultural, and technological concepts and programs for transitioning to the digital society have been developed by international organizations (UN, UNESCO, World Bank, Council of Europe) in collaboration with governments of countries [1].

With the adoption of the "Digital Economy" program in August 2017, the concepts of "digital literacy" and "digital competence" were introduced. Let's explore the similarities and differences between the concepts of ICT competence and digital competence.

The job functions of an educator imply proficiency in ICT competencies. ICT competencies for educators can be divided into two spheres of activity: technology mastery of information technologies and the methodology of applying ICT in the educational process. UNESCO identifies components of ICT competencies for educators, including understanding the role of ICT in education [2], curriculum and assessment, pedagogical practices, technical and software ICT tools, organization and management of the educational process, and professional development. Three approaches to the informatization of educational institutions are associated with each of the highlighted aspects: application of ICT, acquisition of knowledge, and knowledge production. This allows for a comprehensive structure of teacher ICT competencies. However, the content of ICT training should be determined based on an understanding of the current state of information technologies: artificial intelligence [3], the Internet of Things, cloud services Web 4.0, digital (virtual) educational environments, massive open online course platforms, web portfolios, and educational blockchain.

The term "digital competence" was first introduced in 1997 by Paul Gilster, an American writer and journalist. According to Gilster, digital competence is the ability to understand and use information provided in various formats and from a wide range of sources with the help of computers. Continuous presence on the Internet, within the realm of hypertext, enabling rapid navigation from one resource to another, shapes new patterns of human behavior, information-seeking techniques, and communication characteristics. This leads to the formation of network thinking, the main feature of which is a high degree of information and communication activity. Digital competence emphasizes socio-communicative aspects in human activity. Gilster identifies criteria for achieving digital competence, including criteria for achieving media competence, information search skills and tool usage, the ability to

quickly master these tools (information competence) [4], communication skills with other users (communicative competence), and skills in producing information in various forms and formats (creative competence).

Accordingly, four types of digital competence were identified:

Information and media competence - knowledge, skills, motivation, and responsibility related to searching, understanding, organizing, archiving digital information, and critically interpreting it, as well as creating information objects using digital resources (text, visual, audio, and video).

Communicative competence - knowledge, skills, motivation, and responsibility required for various forms of communication (email, chats, blogs, forums, social networks, etc.) and for different purposes.

Technical competence - knowledge, skills, motivation, and responsibility enabling effective and secure use of technical and software tools to solve various tasks, including the use of computer networks, cloud services, etc.

Consumer competence - knowledge, skills, motivation, and responsibility enabling the use of digital devices and the internet to solve various everyday tasks related to specific life situations involving the satisfaction of various needs.

According to the authors, considering motivational, volitional, and value aspects of digital competence opens the way to understanding the nature, structure, and development opportunities of the concept of digital citizenship, laying the foundation for the development of self-regulation in the era of the internet. It's about expanding, not narrowing, the possibilities for individuals who can and are ready to make choices consciously and responsibly (digital freedom of the individual).

A significant component of "Digital Competence," unlike "ICT Competence," is creativity, as the ability and skill to create new information objects using digital resources (text, visual, audio, and video).

Considerable attention is given to cybersecurity. Internet security is considered not only as the ability to protect personal and private data but also as the ability to assess the reliability of information, avoid and prevent risks of information pressure during communication on the internet. It involves not only the ability to protect one's computer or internet access device from global network threats but also the ability to create secure internet products and digital environments for personal use.

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